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Influence of Different Walking Speeds on Speech

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Abstract. The objective of this paper is to examine the effect of different walking speeds on concurrent speech tasks. Entrainment of talking to walking would support a model in which speech production planning is governed by coupled oscillators as proposed by Articulatory Phonology and Task Dynamics. The experimental design involved a walking-while-talking paradigm with three different gait velocities (normal, fast, slow) and two different speech tasks – reading aloud and repeated syllable production. Participants were 32 adults between 18 and 32 (mean age 22.5 ± 2.9 years) with no neurological, physiological, or psychological conditions impacting speech and/or gait. Results indicated that walking speed significantly affected speech measures in both tasks, but the effect size was considerably smaller for talking than gait. The effect of gait velocity was numerically much greater in the Syllable condition than in the Prose condition. This may show entrainment of talking to walking, supporting an oscillatory model of speech production. But the model would need to explain why speech did not change to the same extent as gait. Conversely, non-oscillatory models need to account for the fact that walking speed influenced speech in the first place.

Plain English Abstract. Does our brain have a “metronome” for speech? According to the Articulatory Phonology and Task Dynamics model, the timing with which we produce speech sounds is governed by coupled oscillators (the “metronome”), making speech a periodic (rhythmic) action. We know that walking is periodic. If speech were too, the two actions should entrain (converge to the same frequency) when carried out simultaneously, like two metronomes that eventually beat the same rhythm. 32 participants between 18 and 32 years with no conditions that impacted their speech or gait were asked to walk and talk simultaneously at three different speeds (normal, fast, slow). One group was reading a text, the other repeated the syllable ‘ba’. The speed of participants’ speech was affected by their walking speed, but speech slowed down and sped up to a lesser extent than gait. Walking speed had a much greater effect on speech for the participants repeating ‘ba’ than the ones reading the text. This might show entrainment between speech and gait, supporting an oscillatory (“metronomic”) model of speech production. But the model would need to explain why speech did not change to the same extent as gait. Conversely, non-oscillatory models need to account for the fact that walking speed influenced speech in the first place.

Keywords: entrainment; periodicity; coupled oscillators; walking-while-talking; Articulatory Phonology; Task Dynamics

1 Introduction

This paper aims to investigate the possibility of periodic, oscillatory mechanisms behind speech production through a walking-while-talking paradigm (see 2.3). In a walking-while-talking paradigm where participants are asked to produce speech while manipulating their walking speed, one would expect their speech rate to change in line with their walking speed according to the Articulatory Phonology/ Task Dynamics (AP/TD) framework. I.e., we would expect speakers to talk faster when walking faster and talk more slowly when walking more slowly. One might expect entrainment, if present, to be more pronounced during continuous syllable repetition than natural speech, since the former constitutes a more periodic and rhythmic motor task than the latter. Should significant differences in participants’ speech be found between the different walking-and-talking conditions, they would likely reflect entrainment of speech production to the walking speed and thus support the idea that speech production planning is governed by coupled oscillators as proposed by AP/TD.

1.1 The Articulatory Phonology/ Task Dynamics Framework

Researchers have proposed neural oscillators as control structures underlying different aspects of speech production planning, including syllable structure and rhythm production (Barbosa, 2002; Goldstein, 2008; Goldstein et al., 2009; Kröger et al., 2016). The AP/TD framework is one such oscillatory model (for an in-depth explanation, see Krivokapić, 2020). In AP/TD, the basic speech unit is the gesture, defined as ‘a linguistically relevant constriction of the vocal tract’ (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 1). Each of the gestures forming an utterance is associated with a planning oscillator; for example, the word “mad” consists of four gestures: lip closure and velum opening at onset /m/, wide pharyngeal constriction of the tongue body at vowel /a/, and tongue tip closure at the coda /d/ (Goldstein et al., 2009, p. 241; Krivokapić, 2020, p. 2). At the start of utterance planning, the oscillators ‘move’ in a random relationship to each other, but through changes of individual oscillators’ phases, they eventually reach a stable phase pattern (Goldstein et al., 2009, p. 241). In this stable system, gestures are activated at phase 0 of their oscillators, whose relative coupling controls the temporal coordination of the gestures in the utterance (Goldstein et al., 2009, p. 241; Krivokapić, 2020, p. 2).

Syllable structure results from the timing of gestures involved in the syllable, and prosodic structure emerges from the coordination of prosodic gestures (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 3f.). Krivokapić (2020, p. 4) defines two types of gestures: π - and μ -gestures, both of which slow concurrently active gestures, causing a later start, longer durations, and less overlap in gestures which are active at the same time. π -gestures represent prosodic boundaries while μ -gestures control lexical stress (Krivokapić, 2020, pp. 4-8).

The AP/TD approach to speech production has several theoretical advantages. For example, no mediation between phonology and phonetics is necessary, since gesture specifications combine both phonological and phonetic information (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 2). AP/TD also places relatively little cognitive processing load on the speaker, since the movement trajectories of utterances are specified by the task dynamical system once the word sequence, prosodic structure, and rate of speech of a given utterance are planned, so movement trajectories need not be computed (Turk & Shattuck-Hufnagel, 2020, p. 46f.). Further, speakers are not required to plan surface speech timing since it emerges from AP/TD’s coupled oscillator model (Turk & Shattuck-Hufnagel, 2020, p. 47). This phonology-intrinsic timing mechanism allows AP/TD to avoid the use of a phonetic planning component and phonology-extrinsic (general-purpose) timer (Turk & Shattuck-Hufnagel, 2020, p. 47).

1.2 Speech Rate Entrainment

The role of coupled oscillators in speech production may lie in controlling speech rate. Evidence for this comes from studies showing entrainment of speech rate to concurrent tasks such as walking. Walking has been defined as an oscillatory, rhythmical motor behaviour emerging from cyclical neuronal activity in central pattern generators – neural structures in the spinal cord (MacKay-Lyons, 2002, p. 69; Samulski et al., 2019, p. 90). If speech gestures were governed by periodic oscillations as AP/TD proposes, we would expect these to entrain with other oscillators. During entrainment, two oscillators with different frequencies converge to a common period, whereby the weaker oscillator locks into the frequency of the stronger, or, if both are equally strong, they settle on a middle frequency (Pantaleone, 2002; Thaut, 2013, p. 31ff.).

Studies show that entrainment of concurrent motor tasks to walking is possible. For example, Hill et al. (1988, p. 570ff.) tested for entrainment of breathing to walking in 38 participants (18 male, 20

female, mean age 29). Subjects were asked to walk on a level treadmill at 2.5-3.0mph while breathing through a pneumotachograph. The time intervals between heel strikes of the right foot and onset of in- or expiration were analysed, and the researchers found evidence of entrainment between steps and breaths in most subjects. Only eight participants exhibited little to no entrainment, while the remaining thirty showed entrainment to walking rhythm in at least 25% of breaths. Similar results were found by Armstrong et al. (1997, p. 288), who investigated the effect of upper limb movements on entrainment of breathing frequency to walking rhythm. The researchers collected data from eight women (mean age 22), who were asked to walk on a treadmill at 3.0mph in three different conditions: normal gait and two different arm swing conditions in which two contrasting arm movements were performed with 1lb and 3lb hand-held weights while walking. Weight and arm swing pattern did not significantly affect the rhythmic entrainment between breathing pattern and heel strikes. All participants except one displayed entrainment of breathing and walking, with one subject showing entrainment of up to 48% of breaths.

Entrainment with walking has also been found for chewing. Samulski et al. (2019, pp. 91-95) studied the influence of different chewing frequencies on gait in 15 younger (mean age 23.2) and 15 older adults (mean age 66.5). Four gait tasks were performed: walking at a preferred speed without chewing, walking while chewing at a preferred rate, walking while chewing at a slow rate (1Hz), and walking while chewing at a fast rate (2Hz). In both age groups, walking speed was significantly influenced by chewing rate, with lower chewing rates causing slower walking speeds and higher chewing rates causing participants to walk faster. The researchers interpreted this as neural entrainment between the two motor behaviours. However, in the slow and fast chewing conditions, participants attained the desired chewing rate by deliberately entraining to a metronome at the start of each trial. This may have indirectly influenced the subjects' gait timing, so that changes in walking speed may have been due to entrainment to the metronome rhythm rather than chewing rate. Control conditions in which participants are asked to listen to the metronome at different rates and then walk without chewing would have been helpful in determining whether the metronome frequency influenced gait performance. Prebor et al. (2021, pp. 365) used the same walking-while-chewing paradigm in a study with 16 typically developing children (mean age 13.1), with the only difference that fast chewing was performed at 2.2Hz rather than 2Hz as in Samulski et al. (2019). The results confirmed Samulski et al.'s (2019) findings that chewing rate had a significant effect on walking and additionally showed that this effect was stronger in the fast-chewing condition (Prebor et al., 2021, p. 369). The average chewing and walking rates showed a tendency for convergence, suggesting bi-directional coupling between the neural oscillators associated with both actions (Prebor et al., 2021, p. 369f.).

Both Samulski et al. (2019, p. 91) and Prebor et al. (2021, p. 366) asked participants to walk at a preferred speed throughout trials while only chewing rate was consciously manipulated. While their studies show entrainment of walking speed to chewing rates, Maezawa et al. (2020) found that entrainment also happens the other way around, i.e., when participants chew at their preferred rate and walking speed is manipulated. In this experiment, the chewing rates of 12 participants (8 male, 4 female, mean age 24.4) were measured during different gait tasks on a linear treadmill (Maezawa et al., 2020, pp. 88-91). Subjects were asked to chew a piece of paraffin gum at their preferred rhythm while walking at a self-selected speed, a high speed (1.3x self-selected speed), and a low speed (1.3x slower than self-selected speed). Additionally, a baseline for chewing rate was measured in a chewing-only condition. Chewing rhythm in the chewing-only condition was not significantly different from the slow-walking condition but differed significantly from both the preferred-speed and fast-walking conditions. There were further significant differences in chewing rate between all three walking conditions. Maezawa et al. (2020, p. 93) concluded that 'entrainment of habitual chewing rhythm to gait speed occurs in humans'.

If walking entrains with rhythmic, periodic motor behaviours such as breathing and chewing, it is plausible to assume that if speaking is inherently periodic, it too should entrain with walking. Jablecki (2013, pp. 21; 86-91) compared 40 participants' (20 male, 20 female, mean age 23.9) production of real-words and non-words during standing versus walking. They found that articulation rate did not significantly differ between the walking and standing conditions, but that pause durations were significantly longer while standing. Due to the longer pause durations, total rate of speech was significantly slower while standing versus walking for both real- and non-words. Jablecki (2013) interpreted these results as indicative of motor entrainment between speech rate and gait. However, in a model where speech production is governed by coupled oscillators, one would expect all aspects of speech to be influenced by entrainment. If only pauses were to entrain to walking, would this indicate that only speech pauses are governed by coupled oscillators while articulation is not? If so, why should an oscillator mechanism apply to some aspects of speech production and not others?

1.3 Polysyllabic Shortening

Further evidence for AP/TD's coupled oscillator approach to speech production comes from polysyllabic shortening (Turk, 2020, p. 2). Here, an increased number of syllables in a foot (the interval between two stressed syllables) leads to a shorter duration of these sub-constituents (Turk 2020, p. 2; Krivokapić, 2020, p. 13f.). In other words, the syllables in the foot are shorter than they would be in isolated production, so that 'the larger constituent is shorter than expected based on the number of its sub-constituent[s]' (Turk, 2020, p. 2). The foot's duration shows a linear increase with higher numbers of syllables, indicating a tendency towards isochrony potentially due to periodic control through coupled oscillators (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 14; Turk, 2020, p. 2). In AP/TD, polysyllabic shortening is explained as follows: stressed syllables are longer than unstressed ones because the μ -gesture slows the activation of co-active gestures (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 14). Depending on whether the foot or syllable oscillator is stronger, either the duration of the foot or syllable is kept constant, leading to either foot or syllable isochrony, respectively (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 14; Saltzman et al., 2008, p. 180). In the case of foot isochrony, an increased number of syllables in the foot at constant foot duration results in polysyllabic shortening (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 14). According to Kim & Cole (2005), only stressed syllables shorten, but not unstressed ones. This can be accounted for in AP/TD by modelling the foot oscillator as dominant during stressed syllables and the syllable oscillator as dominant during unstressed syllables (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 14). It is important to note that this model predicts a tendency towards, rather than strict isochrony (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 14).

AP/TD's account of polysyllabic shortening is challenged by Turk (2020, p. 2) who does not consider the phenomenon reliable evidence for syllable and foot oscillators since in many experiments, the location of word- or phrase boundaries is not controlled for, making it difficult to unambiguously attribute the observed effects to polysyllabic shortening over word- or phrase-final lengthening. Final lengthening may suffice to explain the durational difference between mono- and polysyllabic cross-word feet, making an oscillator-based mechanism obsolete (Turk, 2020, p. 2; Windmann et al., 2015).

Windmann et al. (2015, p. 36ff.) investigated a corpus of English broadcast speech for polysyllabic shortening effects on vowel duration in words, inter-stress intervals, and narrow rhythm units, the latter being defined as 'the interval between the onset of a stressed syllable and the following word boundary'. Observed polysyllabic shortening effects disappeared at all three constituent levels once within-word position (word-final vs. non-final) was accounted for, supporting the notion that such observations may result from a lack of control of constituent- final syllables in the data. In contrast

to this, prominence and constituent-final position were found to have large and reliable lengthening effects on syllables, which Windmann et al. (2015, p. 39) interpreted as the root of prosodic timing in English, as opposed to underlying oscillator-based periodicity.

Turk (2020, p. 142f.) claims that words without phrasal stress may remain unaffected by polysyllabic shortening or be affected to a smaller extent. According to Turk (2020, p. 4), polysyllabic shortening is strongest in phrasally-stressed words, which are preferentially targeted by the phenomenon. This challenges AP/TD's oscillator-based approach, since if such a periodic control mechanism were in place, compression should apply equally to every constituent of an utterance (Turk & Shattuck-Hufnagel, 2020, p. 143). Turk and Shattuck-Hufnagel (2020, p. 143) propose that rather than reflecting underlying periodicity, speakers may use a set of mechanisms to signal the locations of word-based prosodic constituent boundaries in utterances, one of these mechanisms being polysyllabic shortening.

The evidence presented in this paragraph suggests that polysyllabic shortening effects may be spurious and apply preferentially to phrasally-stressed constituents of utterances, contradictory to the predictions of AP/TD's model of oscillatory, periodic control of speech timing. This calls into question the need for a suprasegmental oscillator model to explain these effects.

2 Method

2.1 Participants

32 participants (10 male, 20 female, 2 other) between 18 and 32 years (mean age 22.5 ± 2.9 years) took part in the experiment. Participants confirmed they had no neurological, physiological, or psychological conditions impacting their speech and/or gait. To avoid selection bias, participants were allocated to two groups, Prose and Syllable group, by sign-up order. Group allocation was subsequently altered as minimally as possible to ensure equal numbers of native and non-native speakers of British English in the Prose group. The native languages of non-native speakers of English were not recorded as native language influence on experiment outcomes was only of concern in the Prose group, where the small number of non-native English speaking participants was so small (8) that a differentiated analysis of native language influence on experiment outcomes did not seem statistically viable. The Prose group had 16 participants (6 male, 10 female), half of which were native speakers of English. All non-native speakers rated their English proficiency at C1 or C2 level according to the CERF framework¹³. The Syllable group had 16 participants (4 male, 10 female, 2 other). English-language proficiency was not assessed in this group since there was no reason to expect an influence of language proficiency on task performance.

2.2 Materials

The experiment was conducted in a public square, relatively wind-shielded by surrounding buildings. For each trial, participants walked a straight stretch of 23.75m, turned around, and walked back to the starting point without pausing, so that they walked 47.5m in total. The start and end of the 23.75m were demarcated using brightly coloured tape on the floor. A mobile phone stopwatch was used to record the time participants needed to walk the 47.5m.

¹³ Please find information on the CERF descriptors here: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/common-european-framework-reference-languages/cefr-descriptors>

Participants’ speech was recorded using a lavalier microphone (audio-technica® ATR3350) attached to their clothing near the face and directed towards their mouth, which was connected to a recorder (H2n Handy Recorder 200M, 44.1kHz, 16 bits) that participants held in their hands while walking. The gain on the recorder was adjusted to each participant’s speech volume before the trials. Participants in the Prose condition were then given a laminated sheet with the experiment text. Head position was not specified for participants, but observably all Syllable participants held their heads upright while most Prose participants were looking down at the text while walking, bringing their mouths closer to the microphone and influencing vocal tract shape; although this was not considered a concern since these circumstances applied universally across all participants and experiment conditions in the Prose group and should therefore not influence entrainment observations.

2.3 Trials

Prose participants were given a text to read aloud (Appendix One) during the talking trials, as well as time to familiarise themselves with the text before the experiment, while Syllable participants were asked to continually repeat the syllable ‘ba’. The experiment consisted of six conditions:

Table 1: *Gait and speech tasks in the different conditions for Prose and Syllable participants.*

Condition	Prose Group	Syllable Group
1	standing while reading the text aloud once	standing while repeating ‘ba’ for 30s
2	walking at normal speed	
3	walking at normal speed while reading aloud	walking at normal speed while repeating ‘ba’
4	walking at slow speed while reading aloud	walking at slow speed while repeating ‘ba’
5	walking at fast speed while reading aloud	walking at fast speed while repeating ‘ba’
6	repetition of condition 1	

During the walking-and-talking conditions, Prose participants repeated the text until they had finished the walking stretch. The normal, fast, and slow speeds were self-selected by each participant. For condition 4, participants were asked to imagine themselves on an evening walk, enjoying themselves and hence walking slower than usual. For condition 5, they were instructed not to run or walk so fast as to get out of breath, but to imagine themselves talking to a friend while on the way to an important appointment. The order in which participants fulfilled conditions 4 and 5 was counterbalanced in each group to account for carry-over effects. To mitigate learning effects, participants completed three trials each for conditions 1 and 6, and five trials each for conditions 2, 3, 4, and 5, so that the experiment consisted of 26 trials in total. Whenever a trial was interrupted due to loud noise or obstructions of the walking stretch by passers-by, it was deleted and repeated as soon as the interruption/obstruction had passed. Throughout trials, the experimenter was explicit about manipulating walking speed with no mention of manipulating speech rate. One session took around 45 minutes to complete. As compensation, participants could enter a prize draw for a £50 restaurant voucher.

2.4 Annotation

The annotation purpose was to separate speech from pause intervals to obtain measures for pure utterance and pause time for each recording, as well as the full speech duration in the Prose group and the number of syllables uttered in the Syllable group. For tangibility of the data and ease of analysis, I annotated only one full repetition of the text in the Prose recordings and focussed on a 20s-interval in the Syllable recordings.

Recordings were annotated using the Praat software package (Version 6.1.12). A script based on Lennes (2011) was used to automatically annotate the sound files to text grids with an interval tier named ‘pauses’ and segment pauses from speech intervals (Appendix Two), as seen in Figure 1. A pause was defined as having a maximum intensity of 50dB and minimum duration of 0.2s. The intensity threshold was determined through previous trial runs to strike a balance between pauses not being detected due to background noise, and low-intensity speech sounds being classed as pauses. The duration threshold was based on Zellner (1994:44), according to whom a duration of 200-250ms is the auditory threshold for perception of a pause. Both breathing and silent pauses were included in the analysis while filled pauses (coughing, laughing, sneezing etc.) were excluded, meaning they were neither counted towards pause time nor overall duration. Vocal hesitations such as ‘uh’ or ‘um’ did not occur in the data. Pauses were checked visually in the spectrogram and waveform, and boundaries adjusted manually where necessary. Common causes for pause detection errors were pauses not being detected due to loud breathing or background noise from wind or passers-by, as well as unvoiced fricatives being included in pause intervals as in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Automatically annotated sound file of a Prose participant, using a script based on Lennes (2011) (Appendix Two).

Figure 2: Segmentation error – The [s] in ‘house’ was segmented as part of the pause by the algorithm. NB: The transcription in the bottom tier is provided for explanatory purposes and was not part of the annotation process.

To set boundaries between utterance and pause intervals, segmentation followed the strategy outlined in Turk et al. (2006:6) of using changes in the spectrogram to define the general regions of a boundary and consulting the waveform for more precise decisions. Vowels were segmented at the start/end of distinct vertical striations in the spectrogram, or, failing this, at the shading onset/offset in the first and second formants. Voiceless fricatives were segmented using the shading onset/offset in the spectrogram or changes in the waveform. The end of nasals was demarcated at the last vertical striation in the spectrogram or at the end of formant structures. The start of liquids was segmented at the onset of formant structures in the spectrogram while using changes in the waveform for precision. No other segmentation decisions had to be made for the data. In some instances where background noise, especially wind, made visual segmentation difficult, sounds were segmented acoustically.

Pause intervals were labelled ‘p’ and utterance intervals ‘u’. A second interval tier was added to each text grid, called ‘duration’ for the Prose and ‘syllables’ for the Syllable group, see Figures 3 and 4. Most Prose recordings contained only one complete repetition of the text, which was segmented at the start and end in the ‘duration’ tier and labelled ‘dur’. Only pause and utterance intervals falling within this time frame were segmented and used for analysis. In the Syllable recordings, the ‘syllables’ tier contained one interval starting at the beginning of the first uttered syllable and spanning 20s. Only pause and utterance intervals falling within this time frame were segmented and used for analysis. The number of syllables uttered within these 20s were counted both visually from the spectrogram and acoustically. The ‘syllables’ tier interval was then labelled with the number of counted syllables.

Figure 3: Finished annotation of a Prose recording.

Figure 4: Finished annotation of a Syllable recording (CONT group).

Interruptions (e.g., coughs, sneezes, laughs, self-corrections, repetitions) were manually segmented in both tiers and given no interval label to exclude them from subsequent measurements as in Figure 5. For Syllable recordings, the time spent on such interruptions was measured and added to the end of the original 20s interval to maintain 20s of uninterrupted recording material for the analysis.

Figure 5: The participant mispronounced the word ‘nearby’ and corrected themselves. This interruption was segmented out and not counted towards utterance time or overall duration. NB: The transcription in the bottom tier is provided for explanatory purposes and was not part of the annotation process.

2.5 Exclusions

During annotation, two subgroups of the Syllable group were determined: eight participants produced syllables continuously while only pausing occasionally (CONT group) as can be seen in Figure 4, four participants paused after each syllable (PAU group) as in Figure 6.

Figure 6: *Pause pattern of a participant in the PAU group. For a CONT example, see Figure 4.*

Two participants varied their pause pattern throughout recordings and were thus excluded from the analysis. A further two were excluded for producing syllables in a simulated conversational rhythm, since their speech did not represent a cyclical action as was the objective of the Syllable task. This left 12 Syllable participants for analysis (3 male, 7 female, 2 other), eight of which belonged to the CONT group, four to the PAU group.

2.6 Measurements

For the Prose group, the following measurements were extracted from the text grids: duration, number of pauses, utterance time, pause time. Measurements were collected as absolute values and individual variation was accounted for in the statistical analysis. Duration represents the time participants needed to read the text once in seconds, number of pauses refers to the pauses made during this reading, utterance time is the time spent speaking during the duration interval in seconds, pause time is the time spent pausing within the duration interval in seconds. Participants' walking time was also recorded, i.e., the time needed to walk the 47.5m in seconds, as well as their proficiency level of English (native/non-native), age, and gender (male/female/other/prefer not to say).

For the Syllable group, the following measurements were extracted from the text grids: syllable count, number of pauses, utterance time, pause time. Syllable count refers to the number of syllables uttered within the segmented 20s-interval. A syllable was counted if the vowel started before the end of the 20s-interval. Number of pauses refers to the pauses made during the 20s-interval. All pauses with a minimum duration of 0.2s starting within the 20s-interval were counted, even if the portion of the pause that fell within the 20s-interval was shorter than 0.2s. Utterance time is the total time spent speaking during the 20s-interval in seconds, and pause time is the total time spent pausing during the

20s-interval in seconds. Additionally, participants' articulation rate was calculated, i.e., syllable count divided by utterance time. Participants' walking time was also recorded as well as their age and gender (male/female/other/prefer not to say). English proficiency was not recorded in the Syllable group since it was not expected to influence syllable production. However, participants' Group was recorded after annotation, i.e., whether participants belonged to CONT or PAU.

2.7 Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted in R, separately for the Prose and Syllable group. Models were fitted using the 'lme4' package (version 1.1-25). The 'emmeans' package (version 1.7.2) was used to compute estimated marginal means. For the script used to produce the figures and fit the statistical models, see Appendix Three.

For the Prose group, I obtained the means and standard deviations for all variables (walking time, duration, number of pauses, utterance time, pause time) with all participants pooled together, native speakers only, and non-native speakers only. I investigated the effects on walking time using a linear mixed effects model with walking time as dependent variable, age, gender, and condition as independent variables, and random intercepts were fitted for participants. This analysis was conducted for all Prose participants pooled together, native speakers only, and non-native speakers only. The `emmeans()` function was used on the model which included walking time values for all Prose participants, computing the estimated marginal means for all combinations of walking conditions to investigate whether the difference between any two conditions was statistically significant. Further linear mixed effects models were used to investigate the effect of level of English on the walking and speech measures. In these models, the independent variables were level of English and random by-participant effects, the dependent variables walking time, duration, number of pauses, utterance time, and pause time, respectively. The effects of different factors on each speech measure were analysed with linear mixed effects models. In each model, the dependent variable was the relevant speech measure, the independent variables walking time, age, gender, the interaction between walking time and level of English, and random by-participant effects.

For the Syllable group, I obtained the means and standard deviations for all variables (walking time, syllable count, articulation rate, number of pauses, utterance time, pause time) with all participants pooled together, CONT only, and PAU only. I investigated the effects on walking time using a linear mixed effects model with walking time as dependent variable, age, gender, and condition as independent variables, and random intercepts were fitted for participants. This analysis was conducted for all Syllable participants pooled together, CONT only, and PAU only. The `emmeans()` function was used on the model which included walking time values for all Syllable participants, computing the estimated marginal means for all combinations of walking conditions to investigate whether the difference between any two conditions was statistically significant. Further linear mixed effects models were used to investigate the effect of Group on the walking and speech measures. In each model, the independent variables were Group and random by-participant effects, the dependent variables walking time, syllable count, articulation rate, number of pauses, utterance time, and pause time, respectively. The effects of different factors on each speech measure were analysed with linear mixed effects models. In each model, the dependent variable was the relevant speech measure, and the independent variables were walking time, age, gender, the interaction between walking time and Group, and random by-participant effects.

3 Expectations

I do not expect age or gender to affect participants' gait or speech in this study, but they are nonetheless included in the analyses for completeness. In the subset of participants whose speech task was to read a text (Prose group), English proficiency may play a role since non-native speakers may struggle to read the text. However, this effect may level out due to each experimental condition being repeated multiple times and participants becoming more practiced in reading the text. Since all non-native English speakers evaluated their language skills at C1 or C2 level, it is also possible that there is no significant difference between native and non-native speakers in this group.

If talking entrains to walking, I would expect the following outcomes for Prose participants: duration of reading the text once might increase and decrease in line with walking time since participants would talk more slowly when walking more slowly and talk faster when walking faster and therefore need more or less time, respectively, to read the text. I would expect entrainment to apply to both pause and utterance intervals, meaning pause time and utterance time would both increase and decrease in line with walking time. I have no specific expectation for the number of pauses made.

In the Syllable group, I would expect the following results if talking entrains to walking: syllable count might be negatively correlated to walking time since participants would talk more slowly when walking more slowly and talk faster when walking faster, therefore producing less or more syllables, respectively, within a 20s-interval. Since the duration of the interval is fixed, I would expect pause time and utterance time to stay roughly constant at different walking speeds. I expect articulation rate to be negatively correlated to walking time, i.e., increase at faster walking speeds and decrease at slower speeds. I have no specific expectation for number of pauses made.

4 Results

4.1 Prose: Did Speech Entrain to Gait when Reading Aloud?

4.1.1 *Did Walking Speed change between Conditions?*

In the Prose group, walking time was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.96$), but it was by gender ($p = 0.003$). According to the model, men needed on average 6.73s less than women to walk the stretch ($se = 1.95s$). The linear mixed effects models for both native and non-native speakers returned significant p -values for at least one comparison between two walking conditions, indicating that condition significantly affected how fast participants walked. On average, non-native speakers had a longer walking time than native speakers by 3.16s ($se = 2.34s$), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.196$), which justifies grouping native and non-native speakers' walking time values together in subsequent analyses.

The average walking time was 32.05s in condition 2 ($sd = 3.85s$), 35.65s in condition 3 ($sd = 4.84s$), 44.71s in condition 4 ($sd = 9.30s$), and 29.89s in condition 5 ($sd = 4.16s$). Medians and distribution of walking time by condition are displayed in Figure 7. The differences in walking time were significant between any two of the walking conditions ($p = 0.0003$ between conditions 2 and 5, $p < 0.001$ for all other comparisons). This shows that participants significantly altered their walking speed in each condition.

Figure 7: Median and distribution of walking time in each walking condition for native and non-native speakers.

4.1.2 Did Duration Entrain to Gait?

A linear mixed effects model with duration as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and level of English as independent variables returned a significant effect of walking time ($p = 6.55e^{-13}$): with every second increase in walking time, participants needed 0.08s longer to read the text ($se = 0.01s$). Duration was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.28$) or gender ($p = 0.38$). The interaction between walking time and level of English was not significant ($p = 0.595$), meaning that the effect of walking time on duration was not significantly different for native vs. non-native speakers. Non-native speakers took on average 1.82s longer than native speakers to read the text ($se = 0.85s$). This difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.048$). Figure 8 illustrates that non-native speakers had longer duration than native speakers across conditions, but that duration followed the same pattern in both groups:

Figure 8: Median and distribution of duration in each walking-and-talking condition for native and non-native speakers.

To read the text, native speakers needed on average 18.57s in condition 3 ($sd = 1.72s$), 19.15s in condition 4 ($sd = 1.76s$), and 17.80s in condition 5 ($sd = 1.60s$). Non-native speakers needed on average 20.86s in condition 3 ($sd = 2.31s$), 21.34s in condition 4 ($sd = 1.97s$), and 19.39s in condition 5 ($sd = 1.65s$).

Since the interaction between walking time and level of English was not statistically significant, I analysed the effect of walking time on duration for native and non-native speakers together: Participants walked on average 25.43% slower in condition 4 compared to 3, but their duration increased by only 2.69%. Participants walked 16.15% faster in condition 5 compared to 3, while their duration decreased by 5.67%.

Figure 9: Values for duration in dependency of walking time in the walking-and-talking conditions for native and non-native speakers.

Figure 9 shows a slight tendency for duration to increase with increasing walking time, but there is no obvious linear relationship. Although the data are spread out, different participants as well as native and non-native speakers display a similar relationship between walking time and duration. These results suggest that walking time affected duration in that when walking faster, participants read the text faster and when walking more slowly, participants took longer reading the text. However, participants' speech did not speed up or slow down to the same extent as their gait.

4.1.3 Did the Number of Pauses change depending on Walking Speed?

A linear mixed effects model with number of pauses as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and level of English as independent variables returned no significant results.

4.1.4 Did Utterance Time Entrain to Gait?

A linear mixed effects model with utterance time as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and level of English as independent variables returned a significant effect of walking time ($p = 1.45e^{-07}$): with every second increase in walking time, participants had a 0.05s longer utterance time ($se=0.008894s$). Utterance time was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.69$) or gender ($p = 0.22$). The interaction between walking time and level of English was not significant ($p = 0.0503$), meaning that the effect of walking time on utterance time was not significantly different for native vs. non-native speakers. Non-native speakers had on average a longer utterance time by 2.21s than native speakers ($se = 0.78s$) and this difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.01$). Figure 10 illustrates that non-native speakers had longer

utterance time than native speakers across conditions, but that utterance time followed the same pattern in both groups:

Figure 10: Median and distribution of utterance time in each walking-and-talking condition for native and non-native speakers.

During one repetition of the text, native speakers had an average utterance time of 16.27s in condition 3 ($sd = 1.31s$), 16.43s in condition 4 ($sd = 1.25s$), and 15.63s in condition 5 ($sd = 1.18s$). Non-native speakers had an average utterance time of 18.79s in condition 3 ($sd = 2.25s$), 18.94s in condition 4 ($sd = 1.04s$), and 17.42s in condition 5 ($sd = 1.83s$).

Since the interaction between walking time and level of English was not statistically significant, I analysed the effect of walking time on utterance time for native and non-native speakers together: Participants walked on average 25.43% slower in condition 4 compared to 3, but their utterance time increased by only 0.88%. Participants walked 16.15% faster in condition 5 compared to 3, while their utterance time decreased by 5.70%.

Figure 11: Values for utterance time in dependency of walking time in the walking-and-talking conditions for native and non-native speakers.

Figure 11 shows a slight tendency for utterance time to increase with increasing walking time, but there is no obvious linear relationship. Although the data are spread out, different participants as well as native and non-native speakers display a similar relationship between walking time and utterance time. These results suggest that walking speed affected utterance time in that when walking faster, participants articulated faster and when walking more slowly, participants took longer to produce the utterances. However, the difference in walking speed is much greater than the difference in utterance time across conditions.

4.1.5 Did Pause Time Entrain to Gait?

A linear mixed effects model with pause time as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and level of English as independent variables returned a significant effect of age ($p = 0.0056$): participants paused 0.19s less per added year in age ($se = 0.06s$). Gender did not significantly influence pause time ($p = 0.20$). Walking time had a statistically significant effect on pause time ($p = 1.03e^{-12}$): with every second increase in walking time, participants paused 0.03s longer ($se = 0.0042s$). The interaction between walking time and level of English was also statistically significant ($p = 0.0084$), meaning that the effect of walking time on pause time was different for native vs. non-native speakers. On average, non-native speakers paused 0.34s less than native speakers ($se = 0.22s$), but this effect was not significant ($p = 0.14$). Figure 12 below illustrates the tendency for non-native speakers to pause less than native speakers across conditions, though there is considerable overlap in values, and pause time followed the same pattern in both groups:

Figure 12: Median and distribution of pause time in each walking-and-talking condition for native and non-native speakers.

Native speakers had an average pause time of 2.31s in condition 3 ($sd = 0.61s$), 2.72s in condition 4 ($sd = 0.66s$), and 2.17s in condition 5 ($sd = 0.54s$). Non-native speakers had an average pause time of 2.07s in condition 3 ($sd = 0.48s$), 2.40s in condition 4 ($sd = 0.70s$), and 1.97s in condition 5 ($sd = 0.56s$).

Due to the significant interaction, native and non-native speakers were analysed separately for the effect of walking time on pause time: Participants walked on average 25.43% slower in condition 4 compared to 3, and their pause time increased by 18.11% for native, and 15.95% for non-native speakers. Participants walked 16.15% faster in condition 5 compared to 3, while their pause time decreased by 5.97% for native and 4.995% for non-native speakers.

Figure 13: Values for pause time in dependency of walking time in the walking-and-talking conditions for native and non-native speakers.

Figure 13 shows a trend for the native speakers for pause time to increase with increasing walking time, while for the non-native speakers, pause time remains roughly constant for different walking times. Although the data are spread out, different participants display a similar relationship between walking time and pause time.

4.2 Syllable: Did Speech Entrain to Gait during Syllable Repetition?

4.2.1 Did Walking Speed change between Conditions?

In the Syllable group, walking time was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.95$) or gender ($p = 0.25$). The linear mixed effects models for both the CONT and PAU groups returned significant p -values for at least one comparison between two walking conditions, indicating that condition had a significant effect on how fast participants walked. On average, the PAU group had a longer walking time than the CONT group by 1.76s ($se = 2.30s$), meaning participants who paused after every syllable walked slower than participants who produced syllables continuously. However, this effect was not statistically significant ($p = 0.46$), which justifies grouping CONT and PAU values for walking time together in the subsequent analyses.

The average walking time was 33.00s in condition 2 ($sd = 3.44s$), 33.33s in condition 3 ($sd = 3.93s$), 40.91s in condition 4 ($sd = 6.69s$), and 28.00s in condition 5 ($sd = 3.28s$). The difference between conditions 2 and 3 was not significant ($p = 0.88$). The differences in walking time were significant between any of the remaining conditions (i.e., 2-4, 2-5, 3-4, 3-5, 4-5) at $p < 0.001$. This shows that participants significantly altered their walking speed according to experimental instructions. The non-significant difference between conditions 2 and 3 had no bearing on the subsequent analyses since only the walking-and-talking conditions were investigated for the speech measures' dependency of walking time.

Figure 14: Median and distribution of walking time in each walking condition for CONT and PAU.

4.2.2 Did the Syllable Count change depending on Walking Speed?

A linear mixed effects model with syllable count as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and Group as independent variables returned a significant effect of walking time ($p = 0.00027$): with every second increase in walking time, participants produced 0.28 syllables less ($se = 0.07$). Syllable count was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.068$) or gender ($p \geq 0.058$). The interaction between walking time and Group was statistically significant ($p = 0.0043$), meaning the effect of walking time on syllable count was different for the CONT vs. PAU group. CONT participants produced on average 25.46 syllables more in the 20s-interval than PAU participants ($se = 9.65$). This difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.022$).

Figure 15: Median and distribution of syllable count in each walking-and-talking condition for CONT and PAU.

In 20s, CONT participants produced on average 51.38 syllables in condition 3 ($sd = 17.23$), 52.65 syllables in condition 4 ($sd = 21.97$), and 57.73 syllables in condition 5 ($sd = 23.69$). PAU participants produced on average 28.1 syllables in condition 3 ($sd = 5.40$), 24.7 syllables in condition 4 ($sd = 5.16$), and 33.7 syllables in condition 5 ($sd = 6.33$).

Since the interaction between walking time and Group was statistically significant, I analysed the effect of walking time on syllable count separately for CONT and PAU: Participants walked on average 22.74% slower in condition 4 compared to 3, and their syllable count increased by 2.48% for CONT and decreased by 12.10% for PAU. Participants walked 15.99% faster in condition 5 compared to 3, and their syllable count increased by 12.36% for CONT and 19.93% for PAU.

Figure 16: Syllable count in dependency of walking time in the walking-and-talking conditions for CONT and PAU.

In Figure 16, syllable count seems to remain roughly constant for different walking times. Although the data are spread out, different participants as well as the two groups display a similar relationship between walking time and syllable count. The linear mixed model outcome, however, suggests that syllable count was significantly influenced by walking time in that longer walking times, i.e., slower walking speeds, led to lower numbers of syllables being produced in 20s. The comparison of mean walking time and syllable count suggests that in the CONT group, this trend is contradicted since participants produced 2.48% more syllables in the slow than in the normal condition. In the CONT group, the increase in syllable count from condition 3 to 5 was of a similar magnitude to the increase in walking speed. In the PAU group, the increase in syllable count between conditions 3 and 5 exceeded the increase in walking speed by nearly 4%. Between conditions 3 and 4, PAU showed a decrease in both walking speed and syllable count, though the difference in walking time between the two conditions was greater than the difference in syllable count.

These results suggest that walking speed affected the syllable count produced in 20s in that when walking faster, participants tended to produce more syllables and when walking more slowly, participants produced less syllables. This means that participants' syllable rate increased and decreased with their walking speed. The difference between walking speeds was similar to the difference in syllable count between the normal and fast conditions. Between the normal and slow conditions, walking speed slowed down to a greater extent than syllable count decreased in the PAU group, and in the CONT group, the syllable count even increased slightly with slower walking speed.

4.2.3 Did Articulation Rate Entrain to Gait?

A linear mixed effects model with articulation rate as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and Group as independent variables returned a significant effect of walking time ($p = 0.0045$): with every second increase in walking time, participants' articulation rate decreased by 0.02syllables/s ($se = 0.007$ syllables/s). Articulation rate was

not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.27$) or gender ($p \geq 0.83$). The interaction between walking time and Group was not significant ($p = 0.47$), meaning the effect of walking time on articulation rate was not significantly different for the CONT vs. PAU group. On average, PAU participants had a higher articulation rate than CONT participants by 1.02syllables/s ($se = 0.66$ syllables/s), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.15$). Although PAU participants had a higher articulation rate than CONT participants throughout, there is considerable overlap in the values, and articulation rate follows a similar pattern across conditions, as illustrated in Figure 17:

Figure 17: Median and distribution of articulation rate in each walking-and-talking condition for CONT and PAU.

CONT participants' average articulation rate was 2.80syllables/s in condition 3 ($sd = 0.91$ syllables/s), 2.89 syllables/s in condition 4 ($sd = 1.14$ syllables/s), and 3.15syllables/s in condition 5 ($sd = 1.22$ syllables/s). PAU participants had an average articulation rate of 3.89syllables/s in condition 3 ($sd = 1.03$ syllables/s), 3.78 syllables/s in condition 4 ($sd = 1.41$ syllables/s), and 4.55syllables/s in condition 5 ($sd = 1.92$ syllables/s).

Since the interaction between walking time and Group was not statistically significant, I analysed the effect of walking time on syllable count for CONT and PAU together: Participants walked on average 22.74% slower in condition 4 compared to 3, and their articulation rate increased by 0.65%. Participants walked 15.99% faster in condition 5 compared to 3, and their articulation rate increased by 14.25%.

Figure 18: *Articulation rate in dependency of walking time in the walking-and-talking conditions for CONT and PAU.*

From Figure 18, no obvious trend is discernible for the relationship between articulation rate and walking time. Although the data are spread out, most participants of both groups show a relatively constant articulation rate at different walking speeds. Some participants, like P19, show more variation in their articulation rate, but without clear correlation between articulation rate and walking time. The linear mixed model outcome suggests that articulation rate was significantly influenced by walking time in that longer walking times, i.e., slower walking speeds, led to lower articulation rates and shorter walking time, i.e., higher walking speeds, led to higher articulation rates. In the comparison of mean walking time and articulation rate, this trend is contradicted since articulation rate increased slightly in the slow compared to the normal condition, while walking speed slowed considerably. The increase in articulation rate between conditions 3 and 5 was of nearly the same magnitude as the increase in walking speed.

These results suggest that walking speed affected articulation rate in that when walking faster, participants produced more syllables per second and when walking more slowly, participants produced less syllables per second. The difference between walking speeds was similar to the difference in articulation rate between the normal and fast conditions. Between the normal and slow conditions, walking speed slowed down while articulation rate increased slightly.

4.2.4 *Did the Number of Pauses change depending on Walking Speed?*

A linear mixed effects model with number of pauses as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and Group showed that the number of pauses participants made in 20s was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.68$), gender ($p \geq 0.13$), or walking time ($p = 0.52$).

4.2.5 *Did Utterance Time Entrain to Gait?*

A linear mixed effects model with utterance time as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and Group showed that participants' utterance time in the 20s- interval was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.49$), gender ($p \geq 0.054$), or walking time ($p = 0.64$).

4.2.6 *Did Pause Time Entrain to Gait?*

A linear mixed effects model with pause time as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and Group showed that participants' pause time in the 20s- interval was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.49$), gender ($p \geq 0.054$), or walking time ($p = 0.64$).

5 Discussion

This study investigated whether speech would entrain to gait when manipulating walking speed. Since gait is governed by periodic control structures, entrainment of speech to gait would support a periodic, oscillatory model of speech production planning.

The experimental paradigm included two different speech tasks, reading of a text and repeated syllable production, which participants executed while walking at different speeds. Measurements were collected for walking speed, duration of reading the text once (Prose group only), syllable count (Syllable group only), articulation rate (Syllable group only), number of pauses, utterance time, and pause time. In the statistical analysis, it was first important to establish whether participants significantly altered their walking speed between different experimental conditions. Then, the influence of walking speed on the different speech measures was analysed separately for the Prose and Syllable groups to establish whether entrainment of speech to gait took place.

5.1 Walking Time

In both the Prose and Syllable group, condition significantly affected participants' walking time, meaning subjects altered their walking speed according to experimental instructions, so that the analysis of walking time had to be done separately for the Prose and Syllable groups. Within the Prose group, there was no statistically significant difference in walking time between native and non-native speakers, and within the Syllable group, there was no significant difference between CONT and PAU, meaning that walking speed was comparable between the different subgroups of the Prose and Syllable cohorts.

In the Prose group, there was a significant difference between each of the four walking-and-talking conditions, including between normal-walking (2) and normal-walking-and-talking (3): participants walked significantly slower when simultaneously reading the text than they did when just walking. In the Syllable group, all walking-and-talking conditions differed significantly from each other in walking speed except conditions 2 and 3. This indicates that reading a text places a higher processing load on speakers than syllable repetition, so that reading slows concurrent walking while syllable production does not. Alternatively, the slowing effect may be due to Prose participants being handed a physical sheet to read the text off, while Syllable participants did not require such a requisite.

Directing their gaze onto the text while walking may have caused Prose participants to slow down to avoid tripping or crossing the boundaries of the walking stretch. Both explanations are plausible and not mutually exclusive. To further investigate how walking is affected by speech, it would be interesting to have participants either memorise a text or talk freely about a chosen topic while walking, so that the additional visual distraction of reading from a sheet of paper be removed.

5.2 Speech Measures

In the Prose group, non-native speakers had a significantly longer duration and longer utterance time than native speakers, but there was no statistically significant difference in number of pauses or pause time. This indicates that native and non-native pause patterns were comparable and non-native speakers needed longer to articulate the prose than native speakers, increasing their utterance time and thus their duration. Crucially, this difference is not due to speech errors, since these were not counted towards utterance time or duration (see 2.4).

Walking time significantly affected duration, utterance time, and pause time in that a longer walking time, i.e., slower walking speed, led to longer duration, utterance time, and pause time. The interaction between walking time and level of English was only statistically significant for pause time, but not duration and utterance time. Walking time did not have a significant effect on number of pauses, suggesting that walking speed did not affect the number of pauses participants made during one repetition of the text. Since number of pauses was constant but pause time changed, we can conclude that slower walking speeds led to longer pause durations rather than more pauses, and faster walking speeds led to shorter pause durations rather than less pauses.

If talking entrains to walking, I expected to see duration, utterance time, and pause time increase and decrease in line with walking time. It is true that these speech measures increased with increasing walking time, i.e., with slower walking speeds, and that this effect was statistically significant. However, the speech measures did not change to the same extent as walking time. Pause time is the only variable which increased by nearly the same percentage as walking time between the normal and slow conditions. Overall, the effect size was much greater for walking time than for the speech measures. If entrainment were happening, I would expect the effect to be of a similar magnitude for walking and talking.

In the Syllable group, CONT speakers had a significantly higher syllable count, lower number of pauses, higher utterance time, and lower pause time than PAU speakers, but there was no statistically significant difference in articulation rate. These differences are to be expected since PAU participants paused after every syllable while CONT participants only paused occasionally. The increased number of pauses led to a higher pause time and thereby lower utterance time of PAU speakers in the 20s-interval. Since PAU speakers had a shorter utterance time than CONT speakers, but both groups articulated syllables at the same rate, it follows that CONT participants had a significantly higher syllable count.

Walking time significantly affected syllable count and articulation rate in that a longer walking time, i.e., slower walking speed, led to lower syllable count and articulation rate. The interaction between walking time and Group was statistically significant for syllable count but not articulation rate. Walking time did not have a significant effect on number of pauses, utterance time, or pause time.

If talking entrains to walking, I expected to see a negative correlation of syllable count and articulation rate to walking time, which is indeed the case. I expected utterance time and pause time to stay roughly constant since the length of the analysed interval was fixed at 20s and it is plausible for the proportions of utterance time and pause time to stay the same at different walking speeds. Since

walking time did not significantly influence utterance time or pause time, this prediction was met. Walking time did not significantly affect number of pauses, suggesting that walking speed did not affect the number of pauses participants made in 20s.

Although syllable count and articulation rate increased at faster and decreased at slower walking speeds, the magnitude of this change is much smaller for talking than walking between the normal and slow conditions. Against predictions, CONT speakers' syllable count and articulation rate increased slightly in the slow compared to the normal condition, although the effect size is so small that it may be functionally negligible. In the fast compared to the normal condition, the increase in syllable count and articulation rate was of a similar extent to the increase in walking speed.

5.3 Results in the Theoretical Context

These results show that walking speed influenced speech in a way that resembles entrainment of talking to walking, and that this effect was statistically significant. Walking speed affected pause time as well as utterance time and articulation rate, contradicting the results in Jablecki (2013) where only pause durations entrained to walking. These results are in line with the expectation that entrainment of speech to gait should apply to all aspects of speech since it would seem implausible for a coupled oscillator system to guide pause duration but not articulation. However, the effect size for the changes between conditions was much smaller for speech than gait, even though if talking entrained to walking, we would expect both to change to the same extent. The only instances in which the difference in speech measures was comparable to the difference in walking speed was for the comparison between the normal and fast conditions in the Syllable group and the normal-slow comparison in the Prose group – though in the latter case, this applied only to pause time, not utterance time or duration. This indicates that entrainment of speech and gait may be more likely to occur during syllable repetition, since it constitutes a more periodic, rhythmic motor task than natural speech.

Although the patterns in the data are not clear enough to say with certainty that talking entrains to walking and that speech planning is thus guided by coupled oscillators, the effects of gait on speech found in this experiment would need to be accounted for in a model of speech production. While the formulation of an alternative model lies outwith the scope of this study, for non-oscillatory approaches to speech production planning, see Turk & Shattuck-Hufnagel (2020).

5.4 General Shortcomings of this Study

Due to COVID-19 restrictions, data collection took place outdoors in a public space. This led to background noise from wind, machines, passers-by etc. in the recordings, making annotation difficult in certain instances. A more accurate annotation may be achieved with recordings made in a sound-controlled environment.

Further, the participant cohort was relatively small with, after exclusions, 16 participants in the Prose group, eight of which were native and eight non-native speakers, and 12 participants in the Syllable group, eight of which fell in the CONT and four in the PAU group. It would be interesting to conduct the same experiment with a larger participant cohort to confirm whether the findings reflect general behavioural patterns or are specific to the speakers who happened to take part in this study.

Any future experiments of this kind should also control for speech behaviour in the Syllable condition. Although all Syllable participants were given the same instructions, eight produced syllables continuously (CONT), four paused after each syllable (PAU), two varied in their pause

patterns (excluded), and two simulated a conversational rhythm (excluded). This variability indicates that more precise instructions may have been needed when conducting the experiment.

A conceivable reason for the effect size of walking speed on speech being smaller than might be expected in the case of entrainment of the two motor behaviours could be the speech intervals that were chosen for analysis. In both the Prose and Syllable group, speech measurements were taken from intervals at the start of the recordings. It may be that entrainment of speech to gait takes a certain adaptation phase and that a bigger effect size on speech would have been observed if experiment conditions had been longer and speech intervals for analysis taken 10s, 20s or even 30s after the onset of speech production.

6 Conclusion

This paper has introduced the AP/TD model of speech production planning with a focus on its coupled oscillator mechanism. If speech is governed by coupled oscillators, I expected it to entrain to a rhythmic action such as walking. Previous papers have shown that entrainment of other motor behaviours to walking is possible and have even found entrainment of speech to gait, although this effect was limited to pauses – contradictory to AP/TD's predictions.

The current study employed a walking-while-talking paradigm in which participants walked at different speeds while either reading a text or repeatedly producing the syllable 'ba'. Entrainment of speech to gait, if present, was expected to be more pronounced during the syllable production task due to its repetitive nature.

In the Prose group, a statistically significant effect of gait on overall duration, utterance time, and pause time was found. Each of these speech measures increased at slower and decreased at faster walking speeds. In the Syllable group, walking speed had a statistically significant effect on the syllable count produced in 20s and participants' articulation rate. Both syllable count and articulation rate were lower at slower walking speeds and higher at faster walking speeds.

These effects might be interpreted as entrainment of speech to gait, however, the change in speech measures was much smaller in magnitude than the change in walking speed between different walking conditions. If entrainment were happening, one would expect speech to change to a similar extent as gait. The only instances in which this was the case were for pause time – but not utterance time or overall duration – between the normal- and slow-walking conditions in the Prose group, and for syllable count and articulation rate between the normal- and fast-walking conditions in the Syllable group. This indicates a more stable entrainment pattern during repetitive syllable production than prose.

In conclusion, speech was clearly influenced by gait velocity in a statistically significant way in this experiment – a finding which supports a coupled oscillator model of speech production. However, an oscillatory model would have to account for the fact that for the most part, the effect size on speech measures was much smaller than the changes in gait. On the other hand, non-oscillatory models would need to explain why a significant influence of walking on speech was found in the first place. A repetition of this experiment with a larger participant cohort is recommended to establish the generalisability of these results.

7 References

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8 Appendices

8.1 Appendix One

Text read by participants in the Prose group:

The site where Old College now stands was known as the Kirk O’Fields in the 16th century. In 1567, Lord Darnley was lodging in the house. At 2 in the morning, barrels of gunpowder exploded under his room. The bodies of Darnley and his servant were later found in a nearby orchard. Somehow, they had escaped the house, but exactly how they were murdered remains a mystery.

8.2 Appendix Two

Praat script used to annotate sound files, based on Lennes (2011): <https://osf.io/smw9>

8.3 Appendix Three

R script used to produce figures & fit statistical models: <https://osf.io/q8ru6>

About the Author

Adela Bartlick Salcedo graduated from the University of Edinburgh with a first-class MA (Hons) in Linguistics and English Language in 2022. Though presently removed from academia, she continues to follow her passion for phonetics by integrating it into her musical career as a singer wherever she can.

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